

1 Thematic Analysis of Interview Data

The thematic analysis of the interview data started with the transcription of the audio data using different online tools, such as Microsoft Word. The reviewed and transcribed data were then organized into various sections according to the interview questions. Also, interview questions were structured around certain themes and placed in these categories. After that, initial codes were generated by gathering all relevant information for each code. Next, every code was attached with some potential theme(s), whether one of those already set by the questions or another created for that code. This method covered all of the interview datasets. Thereafter, developed themes were gone through to avoid duplication of codes and themes that are similar. The research questions were matched with the codes and themes that were found.

Themes and sub-themes for RQ1

- **Difference between AI and conventional software development**
 - **Agility & flexibility in AI development:** This sub-theme shows the importance of adaptability in AI software development, given its fast evolution. To achieve this objective, it is necessary to utilize a strategic approach that incorporates agile and modular approaches in AI development in comparison to conventional software development methods. (Code: Modular development for Adaptability)

Participant 1: *We take a more modular approach to developing AI software because the landscape is changing so fast.*
 - **Data privacy concerns in AI:** This sub-theme emphasizes the responsibility of developers to take into account the complexities of data usage, privacy, and consent in AI projects, which are more pronounced in AI development compared to non-AI software development. (Code: Data ethics in AI vs. non-AI development)

Participant 2: *The biggest difference, in my opinion, is that if you do not deal with data, you do not need to consider the implications of the data you use.*
 - **Minimal distinction between conventional software and AI development:** This sub-theme reflects the fact that some participants believe that AI tools and models can be integrated into their current workflow, and they do not see significant differences in the nature of the work or between AI and software development practices. (Code: Integration of AI in software engineering with minimum difference)

Participant 1: *For most programmers, it's just another API. We don't have to worry about how vectorization works if we don't want to or you can dive deep within the different AI aspects of programming.*

- **Analytical insights needed in AI:** This sub-theme emphasizes the importance of analytical approaches for understanding and interpreting data in AI development, whereas functional approaches are the focus of conventional software development. (Code: Differences between AI and conventional software engineering)

Participant 7: *I think they're a bit different when people work more with AI.*

- **Probabilistic nature of AI development:** This sub-theme shows a distinction between AI and conventional software development, that is the unpredictability of results in AI software development, despite the overall similarity in their processes. (Code: Similarity of processes in AI and software development)

Participant 3: *The results are sometimes not exactly what you expect, as in conventional software development. The process is fairly similar to what I've done before, but the specifics and details are different.*

- **Ethical prioritization in AI:** This sub-theme emphasizes the high-priority ethical aspects that must be considered in AI ethics, including data privacy first, followed by transparency, security, and biases. (Code: Hierarchical ethical concerns)

Participant 3: *The first thing that comes to my mind is the data privacy of the users. Then comes transparency on how we process this data, then security, ethics, and biases.*

- **Differences between AI and conventional software decision-making**

- **Uncertainty in AI decision-making:** This sub-theme emphasizes the tendency of AI systems to change, which leads to unexpected results when compared to conventional software development. As a result, there is a need for a more cautious and iterative approach to decision-making throughout the different phases of AI development. (Code: Uncertainty in AI models)

Participant 7: *You don't know what will happen until you have a model. Then you see how that model behaves.*

- **Navigating new decision-making aspects (data) in AI:** This sub-theme explains the importance of data in decision-making in AI software development. The data not only drives the functionality of the system but also shapes the behavior of the system and its learning process and adaptability. (Code: Qualitative differences in AI development with conventional software development)

Participant 2: *The key difference I would say is that decision-making around data.*

- **Enhancing decision-making in AI development with evaluation:** This sub-theme emphasizes the need for an additional evaluation step in the AI development life cycle where the viability, ethical implications, and functional quality of AI models are continuously evaluated. (Code: Critical evaluation phase in AI)

Participant 7: *I think it's more critical when it comes to AI. When you do the analysis, what does your solution do and is this something that we need to do?*

- **Embedding ethical perspectives early in AI project:** This sub-theme emphasizes the importance of taking a strategic approach to embedding ethical considerations in the early stages of development, such as including disclaimers and user responsibility guidelines during the design phase. (Code: Ethical considerations in design phase)

Participant 1: *The allocation of resources to prioritize ethical aspects is mainly done from the design phase.*

- **Ethical transparency and control in AI:** This sub-theme highlights the lack of control over AI output and the need for a transparent approach where limitations are openly acknowledged, and users are advised to apply their judgment when working with AI software. (Code: Navigating uncertainty in AI outputs)

Participant 6: *We don't have one 100% control of the generative AI output. We need to build in control as much as we can, and the part you cannot control, you must be transparent about it to the users.*

- **Early decision-making in AI projects:** This sub-theme focuses on the importance of decision-making at the early stages of requirement engineering and design, especially when dealing with AI technologies, despite the uncertainties surrounding their development in the initial phases. This is because AI systems rely a lot on data for training and validation, so decisions regarding the sources, quality, and quantity of this data are critical due to their direct impact on the performance and accuracy of the AI models. (Code: Initial stage decision-making in AI development)

Participant 4: *There are different stages of decision-making and how to do it for AI is a critical and crucial thing we need to think about.*

Themes and sub-themes for RQ2

- **Impact of emerging roles in decision-making process**
 - **The versatility & impact of AI roles:** This sub-theme highlights the versatility needed in AI development roles and the integral role of

Figure 1: Themes and sub-themes for RQ1

engineers in different areas of AI development, including innovation, process optimization, and sustainable business practices. Professionals working with AI software development are not limited to a single area of expertise; instead, they must engage in various roles based on the project requirements. This shows the need for a broad range of skill sets and to be adaptable to sustain in the field of AI development. (Code: Diverse responsibilities, including sustainability)

Participant 7: *My main role is machine learning engineer, but depending on the project, it can span from just pure ad hoc data analysis to doing data engineering to build a model.*

- **Multifaceted roles in AI development:** This sub-theme highlights the expanding scope of software engineering roles in the context of AI, where software engineers are now required to have a diverse set of skills that span conventional development and new AI-specific tasks. (Code: Cross-functional AI application)

Participant 3: *I work as a full-stack software engineer, building a user interface for an AI chatbot. Additionally, I deal with language models and AI.*

- **Specialization as a path to enhanced development:** This sub-theme indicates the importance of specialized roles in providing direction and optimizing current work processes. Specialized roles like data engineers, ML engineers, and AI ethicists bring deep and diverse expertise that improves the overall development process. This will further help in building software with higher quality, as they contribute to better-informed decision-making by providing detailed insights and expert opinions. (Code: Specialized roles enhancing

direction and efficiency)

Participant 4: *The data engineers or engineers, whatever role it may be, but they are here to optimize the activity, on tasks we are working on today.*

- **Evolving specializations within software engineering:** This sub-theme highlights the growing complexity and breadth of the software engineering field, emphasizing the critical need for specialized roles (T-shaped expertise) in AI and data engineering to address specific challenges and tasks. (Code: Specialization in the software engineering field)

Participant 3: *They are absolutely relevant. And we do have a lot of these roles. We have a term called T-shaped engineer. So, like as you mentioned, the umbrella of software engineering can be attributed to many different things, but we engineers have one field of expertise.*

- **Fostering diversity & collaboration in teams:** This sub-theme shows that the diverse backgrounds and experiences of team members enhance decision-making processes and facilitate open discussion and collaborative problem-solving within the team. This is very crucial for developing fair, ethical, and inclusive AI solutions. Diverse perspectives can be particularly valuable in AI projects, as biases need to be identified and mitigated. (Code: Collaborative team dynamics for decision-making)

Participant 1: *We do have an open discussion about everything that the team takes on. And it's open for everyone to ask questions, come up with ideas or just Be a part of the development.*

- **The need for AI management roles in response to AI advancement:** This sub-theme emphasizes the importance of management and leadership roles in addressing the challenges and opportunities of AI integration, as well as facilitating strategic decision-making in AI development. (Code: Opportunity-driven role in AI)

Participant 1: *Just exploring what can be done with AI and we acknowledge that we need to address AI, and someone has to be responsible.*

- **Impact of emerging roles on responsible development**

- **Leveraging collective intelligence for decision-making in responsible development:** This sub-theme suggests that including insights from various team members, like those with less experience or technical backgrounds, into AI integration decision-making processes will improve development life cycle efficiency. (Code: Inclusive decision-making with diverse expertise)

Participant 5: *Experienced developers learn from mistakes, while juniors need guidance on ethics and protocols.*

- **Essentiality of diverse technical roles:** This sub-theme highlights the significance of various technical roles in building a responsible AI ecosystem, where each role contributes unique perspectives and skills to navigate ethical complexities in AI software development. (Code: Important interdisciplinary roles in responsible AI)

Participant 7: *When you're collaborating between the different disciplines then you have to look at the bigger picture and have discussions with more people, and you get a better understanding of how this will affect different people or different parts.*

- **Balancing technical development and ethical needs:** This sub-theme suggests having experts in the team that collaboratively consider the long-term impacts of AI through a critical balance between technical execution and ethical foresight in AI development. (Code: Critical engineering roles)

Participant 6: *I think it's healthy to have people who think about the long-term ramifications of AI development, I think we should work together and figure out the middle ground. And I think that probably will help protect us all.*

- **Institutionalizing ethical considerations in AI roles:** This sub-theme emphasizes the organization's commitment to ensuring that all team members, regardless of their specific roles, are capable of handling data responsibly and in line with legal standards. (Code: Embedded ethical practices in emerging roles)

Participant 1: *They are aware of the need of How to Store data in a proper way, not to break GDPR. So that's something that's been Part of our development process for a couple of years.*

- **Lack of awareness of responsible AI in current roles:** This sub-theme suggests that certain roles within the industry have not yet had significant involvement with AI and lack knowledge about responsible AI practices. (Code: No exposure to responsible AI practices)

Participant 4: *I would say that it is out of my scope. I'm not pretty much sure of what is happening over there.*

Themes and sub-themes for RQ3

- **Personal factors influencing decision-making**

Figure 2: Themes and sub-themes for RQ2

- **Moral integrity shaping technological development:** This sub-theme highlights how personal values, like integrity and the desire to contribute positively to society, shape professional practices in technology development. (Code: Integrity and doing the right thing)

Participant 6: *In terms of software usage, providing a seamless user experience is considered a basic human right nowadays. I think for most of us we were brought up to be a good person, right? I do not consciously evaluate my actions against a set of principles; it is simply a matter of living each day with integrity.*

- **Individual influence on responsible AI practices:** This sub-theme discusses how personal values and proactive ethics in organizations shape corporate practices and guide AI projects toward ethical directions. It highlight the role and transformative potential of an individual within an organisation to promote or transform organisational practises to a more ethically aligned direction.(Code: Personal advocacy for AI ethics)

Participant 7: *The reason I talk about ethics and so on within AI purely comes from my personal views*

- **Personal ethics shaping professional choices:** This sub-theme highlights the influences of individual ethical standards and values on professional decisions, emphasizing the role of personal morality in guiding actions and decision-making within the tech industry. Here

the emphasis is more on the role of personal ethics in decision making process that can change the directions of projects thereby shaping the ethical aspects of the AI technology produced. (Code: Project selection based on ethical impact)

Participant 2: *It led to us turning down a project. Because it was very clear that the impact of this would not be positive for the world in any way.*

- **Application of ethical standards in tasks:** This sub-theme highlights that regardless of the specific job or business context, ethical conduct, especially regarding data privacy and confidentiality, should be a universal standard in all professional activities and operational practices. (Code: Ethical conduct as a universal standard)

Participant 4: *I will be telling ethical is the way what everywhere we work, it should be the code we must have to use.*

- **Values of individuals**

- **Balancing external mandates with internal values & personal ethics:** This sub-theme highlights the contrast between motivations that are externally imposed (e.g., legal requirements like GDPR) and those that are internally driven (e.g., the desire to build trust with users) and how individuals navigate the interplay between them. (Code: Ethical compliance vs. Personal ethics; Building trust through values)

Participant 3: *Sometimes it is enforced to be applied like legal guidelines. So these are the efforts that you must undertake whether you want it or not. But there are some other areas that might be your personal value too.*

- **Cultivating a motivated valued workforce:** This sub-theme highlights the correlation between daily motivation, employee recognition, and the overall value they bring to the organization, highlighting the importance of a supportive and appreciative workplace culture for productivity and growth. (Code: Everyday motivation and recognizing employee contribution)

Participant 5: *Motivation of the employee contribute value to the organization. Recognizing the contribution can boost their productivity.*

- **Personal values as a guiding principle in software development:** This sub-theme emphasizes a development philosophy where placing oneself in the users' shoes is crucial to creating ethical, user-friendly, and privacy-conscious software solutions. (Code: User-centric development philosophy; Empathy in data handling)

Participant 3: *I am always the first user of the software that I built. I always put myself in the position of my client, like how I want my data to be captured and used.*

- **Upholding ethical standards across AI applications:** This sub-theme emphasizes the role of ethical considerations in AI development. It states that organizations must be transparent about the limitations of AI and acknowledge AI’s probability of leading to errors. There is a need for continuous monitoring to manage risks effectively. (Code: Universal ethics and safeguards in AI development)

Participant 6: *You should apply ethical standards so you do no harm to people and be upfront and transparent that this is an AI product and it could make mistakes*

- **Aligning professional attempts with personal ethics:** This sub-theme emphasizes the need for meaningful work that advances professional goals, aligns with personal values, positively affects society, and demonstrates how personal motivation and values affect professional decisions. (Code: Personal growth and societal contribution)

Participant 6: *Am I doing something that challenges myself? And at the same time doing something good, you know whether for the team, for the company, for society. And it needs to be something challenging and stimulating to my brain.*

- **Using AI for societal & environmental enhancement:** This sub-theme emphasizes a driving force behind AI work: applying cutting-edge technology to important societal issues. It shows how the emphasis has moved from being entirely technical to encompassing significant societal contributions. (Code: Problem-solving as a motivation, not the technology)

Participant 7: *AI has become a great tool for problem-solving. Hopefully, create a better world in some way. If it is environmental or if it is social.*

- **Work motivators of individuals**

- **Interest in AI & professional environment:** This sub-theme highlights how personal satisfaction and work environment are critical motivators for career progression in the AI domain. (Code: Initial exposure to data; workplace atmosphere)

Participant 2: *I liked that I enjoyed the work, so I guess that is the motivation for me to continue the same path.*

- **Trend of digital transformation in traditional sectors:** This sub-theme indicates the digital transformation taking place in the traditional sectors which makes it essential for professionals to keep up with the latest developments and use technology to innovate and improve industry standards. (Code: Transition from one sector to another)

Participant 4: *I'm very much interested to learn more about the current trend going on in the IT part, so that is the reason I have chosen this area*

- **Using AI & ML for problem-solving & as efficiency enabler:** This sub-theme highlights AI's potential to be a significant enabler of efficiency and a tool for increasing productivity. It also views AI as a tool that will augment human capabilities rather than replace humans in the job market. (Code: Problem-solving and ML capabilities as motivation; AI as an efficiency enabler)

Participant 1: *It doesn't necessarily replace you as a human or your work just makes you that much more efficient. So that's the main drive behind using AI.*

- **Industry evolution & leveraging it for social good:** This sub-theme emphasizes the change in the industry where understanding AI is now a basic requirement for software engineering positions rather than a specialty and upskilling is necessary to remain relevant in the changing technological landscape. (Code: AI integration and professional involvement; AI as a compulsory trend)

Participant 3: *Not learning or working on AI might mean missing out on opportunities as the trend continues to grow.*

- **Organizational motivators and values**

- **Operationalizing ethical standards:** This sub-theme focuses on the need to translate abstract ethical principles into concrete actions and practices within the software development process, emphasizing the need for ethical awareness from the initial design phase to production and deployment. (Code: Embedding ethics in development and design)

Participant 5: *Developers should have easy access to frameworks with the right mindset. It's crucial for management and all levels to be ethical and educated on data security.*

- **Work-life balance & community:** This sub-theme highlights the need for holistic employee well-being as a motivation factor in organizations. (Code: Societal enhancement)

Participant 4: *Every department is having their own motivational program.*

- **Societal enhancement through public sector efficiency:** This sub-theme emphasizes how AI software solutions can improve operations in the public sector through compliance and efficiency leading to positive societal impact. (Code: Positive societal impact)

Participant 1: *Our main customer base is the Swedish public sector and we help them be compliance and more effective in their work.*

- **The influence of organizational size on ethical engagement:** This sub-theme highlights that commitment to ethical principles varies significantly between companies, often correlating with the company’s size. In smaller companies, ethical considerations might be more integral to the company culture and decision-making processes, whereas, in larger companies, such issues may become less central or more bureaucratically managed, potentially reducing the focus on ethics. (Code: Ethical commitment difference by company size)

Participant 2: *Some companies are very driven by ethics and it depends a lot on the company size. Larger companies seem to be more distant from ethical concerns.*

Figure 3: Themes and sub-themes for RQ3

1.1 Summary of Thematic Analysis

The summary of the thematic analysis is shown in Tables 1, 2, 3.

Table 1: Themes for RQ1

Research Questions	Themes	Sub-Themes
RQ1. What are the main factors that distinguish the decision-making process in responsible AI development from conventional software development, and how do these factors influence the ethical and technical dimensions of AI systems?	Difference between AI conventional software development	Agility & flexibility in AI development
		Data privacy concerns in AI
		Minimal distinction between AI
		Analytical insights needed in AI
		Probabilistic nature of AI development
		Ethical prioritization in AI
	Differences between AI conventional software decision-making	Uncertainty in AI decision-making
		Navigating new decision-making aspects (data) in AI
		Enhancing decision-making in AI development with evaluation
		Embedding ethical perspectives early in AI project
		Ethical transparency control in AI
		Early decision-making in AI projects

Table 2: Themes for RQ2

Research Questions	Themes	Sub-Themes
<p>RQ2. How do the various emerging roles within software development teams (like data engineer, data scientist, and AI engineer) impact the decision-making process in responsible AI development and contribute to the implementation of AI ethical principles?</p>	<p>Impact of emerging roles in decision-making process</p>	Leveraging collective intelligence for decision-making in responsible development
		The versatility & impact of AI roles
		Multifaceted roles in AI development
		Specialization as a path to enhanced development
		Evolving specializations within software engineering (T-shaped professionals)
		Fostering diversity collaboration in teams
		The need for AI Management roles in response to AI advancement
	<p>Impact of emerging roles on responsible development</p>	Leveraging collective intelligence for decision-making in responsible development
		Essentiality of diverse technical roles
		Balancing technical development
		Institutionalizing ethical considerations in AI roles
		Lack of awareness of responsible AI in current roles

Table 3: Themes for RQ3

Research Questions	Themes	Sub-Themes
RQ3. What are the motivations and values of individuals involved in the development of responsible AI systems, and how do these personal factors influence the decision-making processes in responsible AI development?	Personal factors influencing decision-making	Moral integrity shaping technological endeavors
		Individual influence on responsible AI practices
		Personal ethics shaping professional choices
		Application of ethical standards in tasks
	Values of individuals	Balancing external mandates with internal values personal ethics
		Cultivating a motivated valued workforce
		Personal values as a guiding principle in software development
		Upholding ethical standards across AI applications
		Aligning professional attempts with personal ethics
		Using AI for societal & environmental enhancement
	Work motivators of individuals	Interest in AI professional environment
		Trend of digital transformation in traditional sectors
		Using AI & ML for problem-solving as efficiency enabler
		Industry evolution & leveraging it for social good
	Organizational motivators & values	Operationalizing ethical standards
		Work-life balance & community
Societal enhancement through public sector efficiency		
The influence of organizational size on ethical engagement		